

Medullary Sponge Kidney in a Symptomatic Elderly Female: A Case Report

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Abstract

Medullary Sponge Kidney (MSK) disease is a rare renal malformation characterized by cystic dilatation of papillary collecting ducts. Intravenous urography (IVU) is considered the gold standard for diagnosis. Here we present a case of MSK in an elderly symptomatic female with distinctive sonographic features. A 55-year-old female suffering from acute bilateral loin pain attended a Nephrology consultation at INMAS. X-Ray KUB showed bilateral small renal calculi, USG KUB scan revealed echogenic medullary pyramids. Multiple, small, cystic lesions were observed bilaterally alongside bright echogenic structures. Based on USG impression- bilateral sponge kidney with parenchymal renal disease, renal cysts and nephrocalcinosis, intravenous urography depicted ectasia of distal collecting ducts filled with contrast material, which is a characteristic finding in this scenario.

Introduction

Medullary sponge kidney disease, also known as Lenarduzzi-Cacchi-Ricci Disease, is a rare congenital malformation of the distal nephron where cystic dilatation is observed in the collecting ducts and renal papillae [1]. It is usually sporadic, though some cases are thought to be inherited as an autosomal dominant genetic trait [2]. MSK shows slightly female predominance and often presents with nephrocalcinosis,

recurrent UTI and renal stones formation among other features [3]. The diagnosis is confirmed by a thorough clinical evaluation and imaging studies including IVU, ultrasonography (USG) and Computed Tomography (CT). Management is usually symptomatic, with emphasis on controlling stone formation by stabilizing urinary pH [4].

Case Report

An elderly female of 55 years age came to Institute of Nuclear Medicine & Allied Sciences (INMAS), Mitford, Dhaka for having DTPA renogram. She has been suffering from bilateral loin pain for a few weeks and went for nephrology consultation. There, she was evaluated clinically and had several hematological and radiological investigations. Her clinical examination was unremarkable. She was non-diabetic, normotensive, with normal levels of serum Creatinine (0.9 mg/dl), serum Calcium (8.8 mg/dl), serum Inorganic Phosphate (4.1 mg/dl), serum iPTH (34.9 pg/ml) and a normal urine routine examination. On X-ray KUB, bilateral small renal calculi were found and radiologist suggested ultrasound & IVU correlation. Her USG scan revealed normal sized kidneys with echogenic medullary pyramids. Cortical echogenicity was increased in both kidneys with poor corticomedullary differentiation. Multiple

small cystic lesions were seen bilaterally along with bright echogenic structures casting a faint shadow. Based on the sonographic features her USG impression was bilateral sponge kidney with parenchymal renal disease, renal cysts and nephrocalcinosis. Intravenous urography showed ectasia of distal collecting ducts filled with contrast material, which is concomitant with the diagnosis of medullary sponge kidney. With this background, DTPA renogram of this patient was performed which revealed hold up of tracer activity in the pelvicalyceal system of both kidneys. Furthermore, the graph showed bilateral slow excretion and partial washout after administration of diuretic. Glomerular filtration rates were 43.1 and 42.6 ml/min in the right and left kidneys, respectively, indicating fairly normal parenchymal function. The patient was managed symptomatically to improve their quality of life.

Figure 1: Ultrasound image of kidneys showing echogenic renal pyramids, bilateral small cysts and calculi

Figure 2: IVU image at 15 minutes showing ectasia of distal collecting ducts

Discussion

MSK is a renal malformation first recognized in the 1930's by Lenarduzzi [7]. The name is acquired from the classical cysts found within the nephron (usually 1-8 mm size) and appear as "sponges" upon cross-sectional examination [1,7]. Its prevalence is estimated to be about 1/5000 persons and it ranges from 12 to 20% among patients with recurrent nephrolithiasis [5]. The disease is often sporadic, but rarely presents with familial inheritance in an autosomal dominant fashion [8]. It typically presents between age 20 and 30, though rare cases have been reported in neonates. Women are slightly more affected than men [3,4,9]. Our patient denied family history of any renal disease, and presented in the 5th decade of life. The delayed presentation is not very unusual as MSK often shows indolent and asymptomatic behavior [1]. Clinically, most common manifestations of MSK are nephrolithiasis and urinary tract infection, owing to its anatomical characteristics and association with tubular dysfunctions. Urinary stasis in the dilated papillary duct along with hypercalciuria, relatively high urine pH and hypercitraturia may trigger the formation of calcium

phosphate and/or calcium oxalate stones. Rarely hematuria, renal failure and hyperparathyroidism can also occur in patients of MSK [3].

Diagnosis of MSK is based on imaging studies, where IVU is considered gold standard. Contrast medium collection in papillary ducts lead to a classic image of papillary blush or bouquets [9] or brush-like, sometimes linear striations depending on degree of ectasia. Modalities like X-ray and CT show limited diagnostic accuracy, specially without administration of contrast medium [1]. Hence, as urography has been increasingly replaced with abdominal CT in current clinical practice, renal ultrasound may provide a newer as well as easier option in the work-up of MSK. The typical sonographic features of MSK includes hypoechoic medullary areas with hyperechoic spots and microcystic dilatation of papillary zone, with multiple calcifications (linear, spots, small stones) or nephrocalcinosis [9]. Inversion of the normal cortico-medullary echogenicity pattern with strikingly hyperechogenic pyramids and medulla have also been observed [5,9]. Ultrasound images of our patient revealed echogenic pyramids, cysts and nephrocalcinosis, all of which are typical features of MSK.

Renal scintigraphy is not commonly used to evaluate renal function in MSK patients, except for rare incidence of secondary renal failure. Gupta et al. described a case of sponge kidney with incomplete renal tubular acidosis where inadequate management lead to poorly functioning kidneys as evidenced in DTPA renogram [6]. Other than this, we could not find any report on renogram findings in usual less severe cases of MSK. Our patient was moderately symptomatic, and her renal function was not yet compromised. But the renogram curve revealed feature of slow excretion, t-max of right and left kidney being 12 and 10 minutes respectively. She had no evidence of pelvicalyceal dilatation on ultrasound, so this finding might indicate cystic malformation in renal collecting ducts and papillae where urinary stasis occurs in MSK. Hence, we suggested further follow up with Tc-99m MAG3 scan for better assessment of tubular secretion in this patient.

There is no specific treatment for MSK and management is usually aimed at prophylaxis of stone formation, as well as alleviation of symptoms. Oral potassium citrate is given to reduce urinary pH, and prevent calcium phosphate lithogenesis. Lifestyle modifications include increasing water intake, reducing dietary sodium and proteins, increasing vegetable and fruit intake [3]. Rarely, surgical interventions are considered for stone removal.

Conclusion

MSK is a complex disease that deserves more attention and research efforts to elucidate its etiology and optimize management strategies, because every patient is unique and to preserve kidney functions timely diagnosis, proper treatment and frequent follow up are essential. Although nuclear medicine techniques are paths less traversed for these patients, scintigraphy has long been a time-tested tool for evaluation of renal function. Documentation of renogram patterns and understanding the features might help bring some valuable comprehension of this poorly understood pathology.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest

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